

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF TRAINING IN PREPARING QUALIFIED LAWYERS

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Abstract. This article can manage to demonstrate the purpose of training activities, and the methods of conducting them, the role of training sessions in the development of qualified staff of lawyers who are in tune with the times today.

Keywords: Training, lawyer, professional development of lawyers, psychotherapeutic training, psychological training, business training, skills, practical knowledge.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается роль тренинговых занятий в становлении квалифицированных кадров юристов, которые сегодня идут в ногу со временем, цель проведения тренинга состоит в том, чтобы указать методы его проведения.

Ключевые слова: обучение, юрист, профессиональная подготовка юристов, психотерапевтический тренинг, психологический тренинг, бизнес-тренинг, навыки, практические знания.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada bugungi kunda zamon bilan hamnafas bo'lgan yuristlarning malakali kadr bo'lib yetishib chiqishlarida trening mashg'ulotlarining o'rni, trening o'tkazishdan maqsad, uning o'tkazilish metodlarini ko'rsatib o'tishdan iborat.

Kalit so'zlar: Trening, yurist, yuristlar malakasini oshirish, psixoterapivtik treninglar, psixologik treninglar, biznes treninglar, ko'niklamalar, amaliy bilimlar.

INTRODUCTION

Events, open dialogues, roundtables, contests are regularly organized at the technical school in order to educate them in the spirit of involvement in the reforms implemented in our country, further increase their political knowledge, and develop law-making.

It should be noted that the coordination of the educational and methodological process of the legal technical school, practical and information-resource assistance is carried out by the Tashkent State Law University. In the course of study, students learn the same subjects as first-year students of Tashkent State Law University. In addition, technical school students, together with their education, organize systematic work on improving the legal literacy of the population through the "Street law" project.

Lawyer – a practical representative of the field of law with higher legal education and the ability to apply legal knowledge.

Training is derived from the English word and means to teach, educate, exercise. Trainings provide practical application of theoretical knowledge. It envisages independent and active learning by the student rather than teaching by the teacher. That is, through the knowledge gained during these trainings, a person's ability to think, his professional skills develop. The training also teaches the listener the ability to attract a person to himself.

MAIN PART

Who is a lawyer? What kind of person is he? In today's fast-paced society, the demand and attention to lawyers is increasing. At this point, a question arises whether a person with any legal education can become a lawyer. Is legal education enough to become a lawyer? Today's time

shows that only persons with a high legal education should be able to apply the professional ethics of this legal field with their skills. As a result of increased attention to lawyers in recent years, requirements for their activity have also changed. In this regard, our country needs young personnel who have interactive knowledge and work through foreign experiences.

Their legal literacy was strengthened by the normative legal documents regarding the provision of legal knowledge. Among them: the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 19, 1994, "On issues of organizing the activity of judicial bodies and courts of the Republic of Uzbekistan". According to the decision No. 18, the institute for improving the qualifications of the employees of courts and justice bodies is established on the basis of the republican courses for improving the qualifications of judicial officers. In order to meet the needs of state authorities and law enforcement agencies for highly qualified personnel, fundamentally improve the professional training and retraining of legal personnel based on modern knowledge, as well as to increase the level of scientific research in the field of jurisprudence, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 25, 1997, , on the basis of UP Decree No. 1791 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 21, 1997 No. 364 on improving legal education, raising the level of legal culture of the population, improving the system of training legal personnel, improving the work of public opinion research by the decision of the Ministry of Justice, a training center for lawyers will be established. Another means of improving the qualifications of lawyers is the organization of collective training. It awakens the ability of individual thinking in a person.

The term training was introduced to the science for the first time in 1982 by Hriyashe and Petrovskaya. Group trainings are organized between 6-8 people on average. Training also has its own laws. These include "Microphone", "Activity", "Expressing only one's opinion", "being polite to all members of the group", "calling each other by nickname or not by title – just by one's own Name-calling", "Gentleness", "Participating in training from beginning to end", "Saving time", "Voluntariness", "Nonjudgment", "Confidentiality". The term teaching comes to us from the English-speaking world.

One of its most influential proponents and educational promoters was Dale Carnegie, who founded a training center named after him in the early 20th century.

The training differs from the lecture In the following ways:

- *the lesson must include not only theory, but also practice*
- *not only your knowledge, but also your skills and abilities are formed.*

Training is a technique development process aimed at forming effective professional activity. On the other hand, training is a form of intensive education that combines the development of theoretical and practical skills in a short period of 1-2 days.

According to the types of training:

1. *Psychotherapeutic training*
2. *Social and psychological training*
3. *Trainings on the formation of skills*
4. *Business is divided into training and other types.*

Training is practice where theory is combined with special exercises and techniques. Experts indicated 3 types of education. Communicative training is aimed at developing individual business skills. In particular, negotiating, planning your time, setting priorities, etc. Personal growth training helps with effective communication and goal setting. The training begins with dividing the audience into small groups of 4-5 people.

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE TRAINING – one of the important features is that it is always held in a group. The features and methods included in the training are the basis for effective training. Training is always a team effort.

In this regard, it is possible to mention that on February 11, 2020, the teacher of the department of social sciences, D.O. Kamalova, organized open lectures on the topic of “Educational training” for students of the 4th year of the Vocational Education Department. The aim of this lecture is to train young people in a professional way, to rationally solve the problems they may encounter in their professions, and to develop the ability to find optimal solutions. The main goals of conducting trainings are to achieve harmony and calmness, to improve the quality of life.

The principle involves the involvement of all participants in the activity-training intensive work. The activity of training participants has its own characteristics, which differ from the activity of a person listening to a lecture or reading a manual on the use of a certain technology.

The purpose of the trainings is to provide an opportunity to acquire the theoretical knowledge that needs to be learned during practical work and exercises, and helps to work together as a group. Forming the purpose of training, choosing methods based on the strategy, preparation of information materials, evaluation of results and other issues are taken into account. Taking into account the time, the analysis of the organization of the training consists in monitoring each participation and increasing the professional competence of the trainees based on practical actions.

As a result of the reforms carried out in our country, especially in the field of justice, a two-week mobile training session will be organized for the legal service employees of more than 60 state organizations and agencies in the Navoi region with the participation of qualified professors of the Ministry’s Legal Training Center. At the same time, it should be noted that, for the first time in our country, proposals for the creation of the “Lawyers’ Club” of legal service employees of Navoi region have been approved and the club’s activities will be started. The goal of this club was to form the culture and skills of dealing within the framework of the “language of jurisprudence”.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, today our day is spent in intense pictures. No matter what part of our life we look at, legal relations are involved. In these legal relations, each person is distinguished by the ability to apply the law as an individual, to use it and to strictly follow it. Training has a great role in the formation of every person. After all, no one enters the industry with full knowledge and potential.

The knowledge, experience and skills gained during his life experience increase his self-confidence along with increasing his knowledge.

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